

Research Productivity of Scientometrics Journal during 2010-2019

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ABSTRACT

The present research paper is based on the bibliometric analysis of 3218 documents published in 'Scientometrics' from 2010 to 2019. The paper carried out various parameters of Bibliometrics such as total publications, totally cited publications year wise share of publications top productive authors, top countries in terms of research output, and top cited articles of the journal. The study concluded that the most productive year is 2018 with 398 (12.36%) publications and China produced the highest research output (22.37%) is on top and Bornmann, L. from Germany is the most productive author with 73 publications. KU Leuven is a top institution and produced 114 publications.

KeyTerms: Research Output, Bibliometric, Scientometrics, Scopus, Top Cited Article, Research Performance

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INTRODUCTION

Research is the cycle of investigations which add up further knowledge in already facts. It promotes to review already established sources and collect nascent data from ongoing works. A researcher thus explores a variety of informational sources to collect information about already researches made in an interesting field. Among these sources, research articles published in different journals are considered the first authentic information sources to collect data. If a researcher is willing to know the latest trends in any field of study, bibliometric studies are proved useful to let him know the measurement of the publication pattern of all types of documents during different periods. "Bibliometrics is a set of methods to quantitatively analyze scientific and technological literature." (Bellis, 2009) Therefore, the present study has been considered to find out the research output or latest publishing trends of library science discipline through bibliometric techniques by selecting one of the core journal of this field Titled "Scientometrics".

Source Journal

Scientometrics is a peer-reviewed journal that covers Scientometrics studies related to science and scientific communication. It is a monthly publication that publishes original studies, short communications,

preliminary reports, review papers, letters to the editor, and book reviews on Scientometrics. It is published by Akadémiai Kiadó and Springer Science and was started in 1978. The very first chief editor of the journal was Tibor Braun. The present chief editor is Wolfgang Glanzel. The publications of the journal are indexed in various abstracting and indexing databases.

METHODOLOGY

In this present study, documents published in the "Scientometrics" journal from 2010 to 2019 have been analyzed. The data has been extracted from the largest abstracting and citation database of peer-reviewed literature which is the Scopus database. The data was extracted from the Scopus on 27 January 2020 using the term "Scientometrics" in string 'source title' and afterward followed by a few filters like year, source title, etc. The data was shifted to MS-Excel for analysis and presented in tabular form for further analysis and interpretations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many bibliometric studies have been explored for the present study but a few which were found relevant are presented in the following paragraphs.

Khanna, et al. after studied 'Journal of Academic Librarianship' (JAL) during the

period 2007-2016 found fourteen countries contributed collectively (94.36%) publications and USA contribution was highest (89.85%), K. Coyle and G. Little with were most productive authors with 9 articles each¹. Kumari, et al. conducted a bibliometric study on 'Journal of Documentation' using Scopus database and found 2015 as a most productive year with 63(11.37%) research output, publications average citations received by the articles were 13.05% and the UK was on top with 26.53% contribution in total research output². Thanuskodi in his study of Library Herald" for the years 2006 to 2010 found that out of 138 articles single author contributed 72 (52.17%) articles while 66 (47.83%) articles were published in joint authorship³. India contributed highest with 89.85 percent while other countries contributed (10.15%) of publications. Chang & Huang in their study conducted from 1978 to 2007 found that most of the LIS researchers contributed publication in co-authorship⁴. The degree of interdisciplinary was found ranging from (0.61 to 0.82) with citation to references in all articles being the highest and that of co-authorship being the lowest. Kaur studied the publications of the Malaysian Journal of Library & Information Science ranged from 1996 to 2000 and found the average number of references per article was (22.5) and the average length was (41.2) purely tentative pages. Malaysian academics made the highest contribution and single-authored articles. Mahapatra, G. & Das, B. analyzed the growth of publications on geology during 1987-1996 and found the year 1989 attained the peak of value 551 (11.45%) publications. In the authorship pattern, (36.58%) was contributed by two authors, (29.16%) was contributed by single authors, and the rest by three and more than three authors.

A few other studies conducted by Siwach & Parmar⁵; Tripathi & Garg, etc.⁶ were also consulted for interpreting and analysis of data.

OBJECTIVES

- To identify the total output and citations of the journal
- To find out the year-wise distribution of research output
- To identify the most prolific authors of the Scientometrics journal
- To find out the top ten countries produced more research output
- To identify top-cited articles of Scientometrics

DATA ANALYSIS

Yearly Distribution of Research Output and Citations

Table 1 shows the year wise distribution of research

Table 1: Year Wise Distribution of Papers and Citations

Year	TP	% age	TC	% age	ACPP
2019	337	10.47	225	0.53	0.67
2018	398	12.36	1371	3.26	3.44
2017	393	12.21	2858	6.79	7.27
2016	379	11.77	4017	9.55	10.59
2015	326	10.13	3874	9.21	11.88
2014	397	12.33	6098	14.49	15.36
2013	263	8.17	4557	10.83	17.32
2012	267	8.29	5349	12.71	20.03
2011	225	6.99	5952	14.15	26.45
2010	233	7.24	7756	18.44	33.28
Total	3218	--	42057	--	--

publications and citations received during 2010-2019. It is very clear from the table that there was not a consistent increase in the growth of publications during the period under study. The most productive year was 2018 with 398(12.36%) publications followed by 2014 (12.33%) and 2017 (12.21%) publications. Less contribution concerning publications were made in the year 2011 i.e 225 (6.99%) publications. More citations to the publications were noted for the year 2010 with 7756 (18.44%) followed by 2014 with 6098(14.49%). ACPP was found highest in the year 2010 (33.28%) followed by 2011 (26.45%)

Top Ten Authors

The list of top ten authors who gave the highest contribution to Scientometrics during the period 2010-2019 is given in table 2. In terms of the number of publications, Bormann, L. is the most productive author with 73 publications followed by Glanzel, W. with 62 publications. It is also noticed that these ten authors collectively produced 12.27 percent research output of total publications and received a little more percentage of citations (14.57%). ACPP of Thelwall, M. is highest (25.47) followed by Leydesdorff, L. (21.05). It is also noticeable that among the top ten authors, two were from KU Leuven, 3000 Leuven, Belgium.

Table 2: Top Prolific Authors

Authors	TP	%age	TC	%age	ACPP	Affiliation	Country
Bornmann, L	73	18.48	890	14.52	12.19	Administrative Headquarters of the Max Planck Society, Munich	Germany
Glanzel, W.	62	15.70	829	13.52	13.37	KU Leuven, 3000 Leuven	Belgium
Leydesdorff, L.	41	10.38	863	14.08	21.05	Universiteit van Amsterdam	Netherland
Abramo, G.	39	9.87	740	12.07	18.97	Asia University Taiwan, Wufong, T	Taiwan
Thelwall, M.	36	9.11	917	14.96	25.47	University of Wolverhampton, Wolverhampton	UK
Prathap, G.	35	8.86	313	5.11	8.94	A P J Abdul Kalam Technological University, Thiruvananthapuram	India
Rousseau, R.	30	7.59	344	5.61	11.47	KU Leuven, 3000 Leuven	Belgium
Park, H.W.	29	7.34	467	7.62	16.10	Yeungnam University, Gyeongsan,	SouthKorea
Guan, J.	25	6.33	376	6.13	15.04	South China University of Technology, Guangzhou	China
Huang, M.H.	25	6.33	391	6.38	15.64	National Taiwan University, Taipei	Taiwan
Total	395	100	6130	100	--	--	
%age	12.27		14.57		--	--	

Country Wise Research Output

Table 3 shows the top ten countries in terms of research publications in the Scientometrics journal for ten years. As per the table, China produced the highest research output (22.37%) followed by United States (17.58%) and Spain (12.34%). UK and Germany contributed almost equal publications i.e. (8.77%) and (8.43%) respectively. Four countries namely Netherland, Taiwan, Italy, and Belgium contributed nearly 6% publications each i.e. (6.65%, 6.62%, 6.23%, and 6.19%) respectively. South Korea contributed (4.82%) of publications of total research output. It is also noteworthy finding that these ten countries collectively contributed more than (80%) of the research output of total output.

Table 3: Top Ten Countries in Terms of Research Publications

Country	TP	%age
China	589	22.37
United States	463	17.58
Spain	325	12.34
United Kingdom	231	8.77
Germany	222	8.43
Netherlands	175	6.65
Taiwan	174	6.62
Italy	164	6.23
Belgium	163	6.19
South Korea	127	4.82
Total	2633	100
% age		81.82

○ Institutions' Research Output

Table 5 lists the top ten institutions that made the highest contribution in terms of research output during 2010-2019 in the journal. These top 10 institutions collectively produced more than 20% of the total research output of the journal. Among the top 10 institutes, KU Leuven contributed highest with 114 papers (16.19%) followed by Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas 79 papers (11.22%). Contribution of Magyar Tudományok Akadémia and Wuhan University was more than 10% each while the other 6 institutes contributed less than 10% each. The institution at the 10th position contributed (7.67%) research output with 54 publications.

○ Top Cited Papers

Table 4: Top ten institutions in terms of research publications

Institution	TP	%age
KU Leuven	114	16.19
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	79	11.22
Magyar Tudományok Akadémia	75	10.65
Wuhan University	74	10.51
Universidad de Granada	70	9.94
Administrative Headquarters of the Max Planck Society	68	9.66
Dalian University of Technology	58	8.24
Leiden University	57	8.10
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	55	7.81
Chinese Academy of Sciences	54	7.67
Total	704	100
%age	21.87	

Table 5: Top Cited Papers

Papers	Author	Year	Cited by	%age
Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping	van Eck, N.J., Waltman, L.	2010	1206	33.98
Negative results are disappearing from most disciplines and countries	Fanelli, D.	2012	394	11.10
The rate of growth in scientific publication and the decline in coverage provided by science citation index Open Access	Larsen, P.O., von Ins, M.	2010	390	10.99
The journal coverage of Web of Science and Scopus: a comparative analysis	Mongeon, P., Paul-Hus, A.	2016	329	9.27
Diversity and network coherence as indicators of interdisciplinary: Case studies in bionanoscience	Rafols, I., Meyer, M.	2010	285	8.03
Google Scholar, Scopus and the Web of Science: a longitudinal and cross-disciplinary comparison	Harzing, A.-W., Alakangas, S.	2016	235	6.62
Impact factor: Outdated artifact or stepping-stone to journal certification?	Vanclay, J.K.	2012	194	5.47
Taiwan's National Health Insurance Research Database: Administrative health care database as study object in bibliometrics	Chen, Y.-C., Yeh, H.-Y., Wu, J.-C., (...), Chen, T.-J., Wetter, T.	2011	192	5.41
How well developed are altmetrics? A cross-disciplinary analysis of the presence of 'alternative metrics' in scientific publications	Zahedi, Z., Costas, R., Wouters, P.	2014	163	4.59
Validating online reference managers for scholarly impact measurement	Li, X., Thelwall, M., Giustini, D.	2012	161	4.54
Total	--		3549	100
%age	--		8.44	--

Top 10 highly cited papers of "Scientometrics" during 2010-2019 are listed in table 5. These 10 papers collectively received (8.44%) citations. Among these top ten papers, the paper "Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping" authored by van Eck, N.J., Waltman, L. received (33.98%) citations while paper at 10th position "Validating online reference managers for scholarly impact measurement" authored by Li, X., Thelwall, M., Giustini, D. received (4.54%) citations.

CONCLUSION

Bibliometric studies are useful to identify the latest trends in any field of study. The present bibliometric study explored the different aspects of the popular journal "Scientometrics" in the field of Library and Information Science. The study covers type of publications appeared like articles, reviews, erratum, editorial notes, etc. during ten years under study, but the majority of publications were research articles. The study shows that Bornmann, L. is the most productive author. ACPP of Thelwall, M. is highest (25.47%), China is the most productive country and ten countries together contributed more than 80 percent research output.

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